

Robust and Efficient Pose Estimation of Pipes for Contact Inspection using Aerial Robots*

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Abstract—This work describes the methodology for detecting pipes and their pose in refineries inspection using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) for remote Ultrasonic Testing (UT). Segmentation techniques such as the Hough Transform and its variations, and Random Sample Consensus have been widely used. This paper is therefore focused on the development of an efficient computer vision algorithm to detect the position and orientation of the pipes in order to land on them autonomously to perform the inspection, by using 3D point cloud information from depth cameras. Applying a methodology based on Random Sample Consensus and point cloud pre-processing to fasten the algorithm performance has led to robust estimations of the pipes and their poses in an indoor testbed using a realistic environment, allowing the autonomous landing and the subsequent inspection.

I. INTRODUCTION

This work is motivated by the need of developing a real-time application to carry out remote Ultrasonic Testing (UT) inspection of pipes, which can be single pipes or pipes in a rack, in refineries for loss of wall thickness. This kind of inspections involve some danger due to the possibility of gas leaks. As the inspections are commonly done by humans, the development of a real-time application to inspect the pipes with Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) is needed in order to reduce the danger of the inspection. Factors such as lighting, the distance between pipes, or the pipe diameter have been considered.

Once the pose of a pipe respect to an aerial platform is known, it is used as an input to the control system, allowing the aerial platform to land accurately on the pipe to perform an inspection. The robustness of the detection and the time to detect them are of great importance. For that purpose, a computer vision algorithm has been developed, combining image processing and point cloud processing to obtain a robust estimation of the pipes poses. The images and point clouds are obtained from a Red,Green,Blue-Depth (RGB-D) camera located at the bottom of the aerial platform. Fig. 1 shows the scenario in which the experimental tests have taken place to validate the developed algorithms.

Segmentation is an important step in many perception tasks, such as some approaches to object detection and recognition. Segmentation of images has been widely studied in the computer vision community, and point cloud segmentation has also been of interest [1].

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Fig. 1. UAV inside the mockup pipe rack prepared for autonomous landing.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II describes the aerial platform and its sensors. Section III describes related works from both image segmentation and point cloud segmentation. In section IV we describe in detail our strategy, which involves a series of steps to do the cylinder segmentation and the estimation of its pose. Section V describes an implementation of our approach, evaluating the benefits from the proposed work, while Section VI includes a discussion about the results obtained.

II. AERIAL PLATFORM SET UP

For the purpose of landing autonomously on a pipe, a customized aerial platform has been deployed. The aerial platform must navigate safely in refineries and be able to land on pipes with a landing gear. Once landed, it must deploy an inspection system for the measurement of the loss of wall thickness.

The aerial platform has been designed with a frame structure composed by four arms and eight rotors with a coaxial design, thus implementing two rotors for each arm. In terms of performance, the configuration is not the most efficient, but given the project's requirements, the selected configuration provides the most significant thrust force with the minimum possible weight. Around the platform there is a perimeter structure, where all the cameras are placed, and serves as a protection against any lateral impact.

The cameras used for localization, navigation and detection of pipes are placed in the perimeter structure. For the localization, three Intel RealSense T265 tracking cameras are placed on different orientations, as it is shown in Fig. 2 at the top. Three cameras are used in order to have triple

Fig. 2. Top: design of the aerial platform, including the three depth cameras, marked in yellow, pointing at different directions. Bottom: aerial platform successfully landed on one of the pipes.

redundancy in the aerial robot pose estimation, since the operating environment may have different levels of detail and could affect the system’s tracking performance. For the active navigation (e.g. obstacle detection and avoidance) and the detection of pipes, three Intel RealSense D435i RGB-D cameras have been placed facing different directions: one forward, one upwards and one downwards. The forward and upward cameras are solely used for the detection of obstacles, while the downward camera is also employed for detecting the pipes on which the aerial robot should land. All the perception and navigation software is run on an onboard Intel NUC8 with an i7 processor.

To land accurately on the pipe and resolve wrong alignment problems, a landing gear has been designed by using a mobile anchoring system, as it can be seen in Fig. 2. For the inspection, on the top of the aerial platform there is a cable reeling system with a servomotor controlled ring to store the cable needed to connect the satellite to the ultrasonic system.

III. RELATED WORK

In unstructured environments, existing CAD-based methods tend to suffer from clutter and occlusion [2]. In semi-structured environments, i.e., industrial pipelines, strategies based on the detection and estimation of parametric geometric primitives are generally more robust and flexible. As we focus on cylinder parametric representations, we will use 3D model-based techniques.

For the extraction of simple geometric shape primitives like planes, cylinders, cones and spheres, the two most common paradigms are the Hough Transform [3] and Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC) [4], which are robust to outliers and noisy data.

A. Hough Transform

The Hough Transform is a method for detecting parameterized objects, typically used for lines and circles in images [5]. However, we focus on the detection of cylinders in 3D point clouds. Even though many Hough Transform approaches work with pixel images as input, this is not a necessity.

The Hough Transform is a feature extraction technique used in image analysis, computer vision and digital image processing. The purpose of this technique is to find imperfect instances of objects within a certain class of shapes by a voting procedure. This voting procedure is carried out in a parameter space, from which object candidates are obtained as local maxima in an accumulator space that is explicitly constructed by the algorithm for computing the Hough Transform.

The Hough Transform comprises a series of different algorithms. In [5], Bormann et al. consider the differences between some of the variations of the Hough Transform algorithm, such as the Standard Hough Transform (SHT), the Probabilistic Hough Transform (PHT) or the Randomized Hough Transform (RHT). The differences between each variation are exposed in Table I.

In this work, the RHT was the most interesting version. In [2], Figuereido et al. propose a cylinder detection and pose estimation method using 3D point clouds and the RHT with a different accumulator than the one described in [6]. [7] shows a similar work using a commercial aerial platform in a low TRL setting and using monocular cameras without depth.

TABLE I
HOUGH TRANSFORM (HT) COMPARISON

	Standard HT	Probabilistic HT	Randomized HT
Complete/deterministic	Yes	No	No
Delete detected planes from point set	No	No	Yes
Easy to implement	Yes	Yes	Yes

B. Random Sample Consensus

The RANSAC algorithm is a general randomized procedure that iteratively finds an accurate model for observed data that may contain a large number of outliers. It performs a precise and fast extraction, but only if the parameters have been fine-tuned properly. In [8], Young-Hoon et al. use this method to shape cylinders in large point clouds. In [9], Frahm et al propose a real-time RANSAC adaptation. [10] makes use of a heavier LIDAR sensor for point cloud generation, which targets larger cylinder radius than most of the ones present in refineries.

RANSAC is an iterative method used to estimate the parameters of a mathematical model from a set of observed data that contains outliers. Therefore, it also can be interpreted as an outlier detection method. It is a non-deterministic algorithm in the sense that it produces a reasonable result only with a certain probability, with this probability increasing as more iterations are allowed.

A basic assumption is that the data consists of inliers, i.e., data whose distribution can be explained by some set of model parameters, though may be subject to noise, and outliers, which are data that do not fit in the model. RANSAC also assumes that, given a set of inliers, there exists a procedure which can estimate the parameters of a model that optimally fits this data.

More recently, approaches based on Deep Learning techniques have been employed to this application as well. [11] presents a similar system using a neural network. We have focused on classical approaches in order to keep the explainability of the whole system behavior, intended for adoption at industrial grade.

IV. STRATEGY

A combination of the RANSAC methodology with point cloud pre-processing is applied to obtain the requested output. In our scenario, a set of unorganized points is used as input, and the output consists of parameterized cylinders as shown in Fig. 3, which are commonly represented by the following parameters:

- Point in the axis (x, y, z) .
- Axis direction (x, y, z) .
- Radius.

Given the depth images obtained from the Intel RealSense D435i camera pointing downwards, the depth camera parameters are used to obtain a 3D point cloud which will be used as the input for our algorithm.

As the perception system must be as fast as possible, some filters are applied to the point cloud to lighten the time to detect the pipes on each frame. First, a crop box filter is applied, which allows to filter all the data inside of a given 3D box, selecting the most centered part of the point cloud within the camera field of view, thus reducing the size of the search area. Then, a voxel grid filter is applied to decrease the number of points in the point cloud. This filter creates a 3D voxel grid over the input point cloud data and then, on each voxel, all the points are approximated with their centroid.

Once the point cloud is filtered, an Euclidean cluster extraction is applied to separate the point cloud in clusters, as it is explained in Algorithm 1. This clustering method separates the elements found in the point cloud, giving as an output every possible pipe in a different set of point clouds.

It is important to tune the radius tolerance value properly to obtain consistent results. If it is set to small value, it can happen that an actual object can be seen as multiple clusters. On the other hand, if it is set too high, it could happen that multiple objects are seen as one cluster. This parameter depends mainly on the dataset. Also, a minimum

Fig. 3. Cylinder parameters considered for pipes detection.

Fig. 4. Top view of the clustered point cloud obtained with the downward depth camera. Each cluster is shown with a different color. The axis represents the UAV coordinate frame.

and a maximum amount of points is set to consider a cluster valid.

Fig. 4 shows an example of the resulting clusters, where each cluster is represented in a different color. As we have set a minimum number of points to consider the element a cluster, if most of the shape of the cylinder is not seen, it will be ignored.

For every point cloud, where each cluster may be a pipe, the surface normals are estimated. Surface normals can be computed using a variety of techniques. In this case, a normal estimation method based on multi-threaded paradigm using OpenMP [12] is used due to its promptness compared to other traditional methods. But surface normals are not always accurate. In particular, points near object boundaries tend to have noisy surface normals or no surface normals, which leads to cylinder segmentations that end before the edge of

the actual cylinder.

Algorithm 1: Euclidean Cluster Extraction

Result: Clusters C

```

Create a kd-tree representation for the input cloud
dataset P;
Set up an empty list of clusters C and a queue of the
points that need to be checked Q;
while All points  $p_i \in P$  have not been processed do
  for every point  $p_i \in P$  do
    Add  $p_i$  to the current queue Q;
    for every point  $p_i \in Q$  do
      Search for the set  $P_i^k$  of point neighbours
      of  $p_i$  in a sphere with radius  $r < d_{th}$ ;
      for every neighbour  $p_i^k \in P_i^k$  do
        if point has not been processed then
          Add  $p$  to  $Q_i$ ;
        end
      end
    end
  end
  Add Q to the list of clusters C, Q = empty list;
end
Return C;
  
```

The problem of determining the normal to a point on the surface is approximated by estimating the normal of a plane tangent to the surface. The solution for estimating the surface normal is reduced to a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [13] of a covariance matrix created from the nearest neighbors of the query point. The covariance matrix \mathcal{C} is calculated as follows:

$$\mathcal{C} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k (p_i - \bar{p}) \cdot (p_i - \bar{p})^T, \mathcal{C} \cdot \vec{v}_j = \lambda_j \cdot \vec{v}_j, j \in \{0, 1, 2\} \quad (1)$$

where k is the number of point neighbors considered in the neighborhood of p_i , \bar{p} represents the 3D centroid of the nearest neighbors, λ_j is the j^{th} eigenvalue of the covariance matrix, and \vec{v}_j the j^{th} eigenvector.

To orient all normals \vec{n}_i consistently towards the known viewpoint v_p , the normals need to satisfy the equation:

$$\vec{n}_i \cdot (v_p - p_i) > 0 \quad (2)$$

After the normals have been calculated, the RANSAC algorithm for cylindrical components is run. As stated previously, the parameters must be fine-tuned to produce the expected results. The distance threshold to the model, the weight of the normals, or the number of iterations are some of the parameters to consider. The distance threshold parameter determines how close a point must be to the model in order to be considered an inlier, whereas the weight of the normals is set depending on how accurate are considered the surface normals.

Algorithm 2: RANSAC

Result: bestFit

```

iterations = 0; bestFit = 0; bestError = large value;
while iterations < k do
  maybeInliers = n randomly selected values from
  data;
  maybeModel = model parameters fitted to
  maybeInliers;
  alsoInliers = empty set for every point in data not
  in maybeInliers;
  for every point in data not in maybeInliers do
    if point fits maybeModel with an error < t
    then
      add point to alsoInliers;
    end
    if the number of elements in alsoInliers > d
    then
      betterModel = model parameters fitted to
      points in maybeInliers and alsoInliers;
      thisError = measure how well betterModel
      fits these points;
    end
  end
  if thisError < bestError then
    bestFit = betterModel;
    bestError = thisError;
  end
  increment iterations;
end
return bestFit;
  
```

In Algorithm 2, RANSAC's pipeline is shown. RANSAC provides as an output the best fit of the cylinder model, that is the parameters of the detected cylinders and its inliers. By using the cylinder's coefficients and the inliers extracted from the RANSAC segmentation, the point cloud which represents the pipe can be extracted. In order to check if the coefficients provided by the segmentation algorithm are consistent with the previous detections, the coefficients of the detected pipe or pipes are compared with the coefficients from the previous detection. If the detection is confident enough, the coefficients will be used to calculate the pose of the pipe.

If more than one pipe is detected, the pipe which is the closest from the center of the camera field of view will be the proposed pipe to land on. Once there is a verified pipe to inspect, it is necessary to determine its pose related to the aerial platform.

First, to obtain the angle deviation, the axis direction of the pipe is projected on to the depth image. Given the projected axis direction and the y-axis of the camera's origin, the intersection of both lines is used to obtain the desired angle, as seen in Fig. 6.

To determine the distance from the aerial platform to the pipe, the kd-tree nearest search algorithm [14] is used. A kd-

Fig. 5. Algorithm Pipeline. From left to right: input depth image, filtered point cloud, estimated cylinder, and output depth image with the detection result

Algorithm 3: Proposed pipeline

Result: Pipe’s Pose

Obtain point cloud from depth image;
 Apply crop box filter to point cloud;
 Get each point cloud cluster from Euclidean cluster extraction;

for each cluster do

 Estimate normals;
 Get inliers and coefficients of the cylinder by using RANSAC segmentation;

end

Check if coefficients are consistent with previous estimations;
 Get closest cylinder to the center of the camera;
 Calculate pipe’s pose;

Fig. 6. Pipe’s pose calculation schema. Left: lateral distance to the pipe and angle deviation. Right: lateral distance to the pipe and relative height.

tree is a space-partitioning data structure used for organizing points in a k -dimensional space. The nearest neighbour search is used to find the point in the tree that is closest to a given input point, which in our case is the pose of the camera.

Given the closest point of the pipe from the aerial platform and the pose of the aerial platform, the lateral distance is calculated performing arithmetical operations by subtracting both 3D points on each axis. As soon as the pose of the pipe is known, it is sent to the control system to navigate to the pipe’s position and start the approach for landing. The overall proposed pipeline of this work is shown in Algorithm 3.

V. RESULTS

This work has been developed using C++ and has been implemented in ROS [15] using libraries such as OpenCV [16] and PCL [17]. In order to verify the results, we have carried out multiple flights in an aerial robotics indoor testbed at CATEC. This testbed dimensions are 15mx15mx5m, and has an indoor localization system based on 20 VICON cameras, that only needs the installation of passive markers on the aerial vehicle and/or along the scenario. This system is able to provide, in real-time, the position and orientation of the aerial vehicle with millimetre precision; the sample rate of data acquisition is 100 Hz. Even though such indoor localization system has not been used for the experiments shown in this section, we have been able to verify the accuracy of the localization system based on the Intel RealSense T265 tracking cameras, but this is out of the scope for the proposed work in this manuscript.

The presented algorithm has been tested on an Intel NUC8 with an i7 processor onboard the UAV, without using the GPU in order to not to limit the applicability of the proposed algorithm. Fig. 5 shows the visualization of the main steps of the proposed method. The test consisted of the aerial platform taking off autonomously and navigating inside a pipe rack, where there are pipes with different diameters and separated by more than 0.15m, as it can be also seen in Fig. 4. Once the pose of the proposed pipe to land on was provided, the aerial platform autonomously aligned itself by applying a yaw rotation, corrected the position error, and finally, landed on the pipe.

From Table II we can conclude that the time needed for the segmentation and the pose estimation of a single pipe takes around 10 ms. When the algorithm is run for more than one pipe, it takes around 15 ms. In this work, we are not considering more than two pipes due to the aerial platform will be flying close to a rack of pipes in order to land on one of them.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Even though there are already some techniques to perform real-time 3D point cloud processing to do cylinder segmentation, in this work we offer a robust and fast solution for detecting and estimating the pose of pipes in semi-structured environments. However, it remains a matter of future work the detection of more complex pipes, as well as pipes with elbows or pipes whose distance to other pipes is less than the one considered in this work. Also, future work is focused on testing our approach for cylinder detection and pose

TABLE II
EXECUTION TIME PER ITERATION

	1 Pipe	2 Pipes
Crop Box Filter (ms)	2.4	2.5
Voxel Grid Filter (ms)	0.7	1.94
Euclidean Cluster Extraction (ms)	0.25	0.65
Normal Estimation OMP (ms)	5.65	8.1
Cylinder Segmentation (ms)	0.36	0.93
Inliers Extraction (ms)	0.007	0.012
Total Time (ms)	9.37	14.13

estimation in refineries, where the results may be affected by the reflection and the illumination.

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